

A Review on Impact of Climatic Change on The Global Environment Aspect.

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Abstract :-

Any change in the climate affects the environment including natural ecosystem, water, temperature, energy and human health. The paper discusses the climate changes on various aspects of environment degradation of forest, mountain, with heavy rainfall increase erosion of soil and makes soil less fertile. The paper also includes the effects of climate changes reduces economic sector of people like agriculture and food security. In the end, the paper put forward some suggestions about how to prevent climatic changes in the environment.

Introduction :-

Climate science is one of the most important areas of scientific research in the world today, and we still have a lot to learn to fully understand this crucial problem (D. Coen; 2019). The impact of global climate on various aspect in the environment will be comprehensive, multi-scale and multi-layered. Global warming refers to the fact that the atmosphere is warming is a sign that the earth has passed and will pass away in the future, and it is happening because of human activities, industrial pollution, degradation of land as well as natural disasters and it will have many serious and potentially harmful effects in the coming decades. The scientific evidence shows a clear picture: climate change is occurring at least in the last few decades and possibly for many decades to come (S.Becken et al., 2017).

Climate change will alter the quality and functioning of ecosystem, reducing their capacity to perform role as important life support systems. The degree of local environmental degradation will influence the vulnerability of an ecosystem to climate change. Degradation of forested mountain slopes in conjunction with intensified rainfall may increase erosion and loss of fertile soil and affect the quality of watersheds. Climate change leads to changes in species distribution and abundance and increase the risk of extinction and loss of biodiversity (IPCC 2001 b).

Some ecosystem are highly sensitive, even small changes can have large effects. Small rise in water, temp, change can cause climate changes for the example damage coral reefs, exacerbating other stresses such as pollution and over-fishing and there by cause a reduction in fish stocks and tourism depend livelihoods.

Change in ecosystem composition and provision of good and services may also

have broad economic effects. Essential ecosystem services of peoples such as agriculture, water and food security.

Climate change is projected to further region, particular in subtopics, due to changes in rain fall patterns and runoff, rise frequency of drought and increase evaporation. As rainfall events are expected to become more intense, affects human settlements and infrastructure. The melting of glaciers has become a serious concern in the Himalayan resion, because of the growing risk of glacial lake out -burst floods (UNEP/ ICIMOD; Bhutan 2000).

Effects of global warming on aquatic communities are currently unknown, but because these communities are strongly tied to their territorial settings. Through energy, nutrients and water (Likens 1985, Minshall et al., 1985), change in terrestrial vegetation could have pronounced effect on freshwater system (Minshall et al., 1983). Agriculture is most important sector of developing countries. Increasing the food demand but climatic changes affects the production of food in agriculture Crosson and Rosenberg, 1989 showed that overall, the future rate of growth in worldwide demand for food and fiber can be met, even with most commonly projected climatic changes. The impact of climate change on food supply varies significantly by regions. In general, crop yield are projected to decreased in most tropical regions due to changes in temperature.

Large temperature change that have now become a reality on earth will greatly accelerate other changes already underway in the climate system, such as changing precipitation pattern, increasing evaporation due to warming, and increasing temperature extremes (D. Koll et al., 2018). It remains to be seen to what extent the extent of this development is reflected in elevated temperatures and extremes, but the fact that

greenhouse gases influence aspect of the water cycle early on provides a strong argument for the role of greenhouse gas emissions in climate change (M.Abdollahbeigi,2020). The models simulating changes in precipitation in the ocean, are relatively robust, with moist regions becoming drier, but not at the same rate. N. Golledge, (2020) started that in addition, it appears that extreme rainfall levels in the oceans, such as in Greenland and Antarctica are useful constraints on future changes, even if they apply to a relatively small part of the world's land area. In the agriculture world likely result in increased energy demand for crop drying.

The production capacity of renewable energy supply such as solar, wind, ocean thermal energy conversion and biomass, is potentially more sensitive to climate change than conventional energy supply. Higher average summer temperature would mainly increase the demand for electricity as use of air conditioning increases. Warmer winters should also increase transport activity and energy demand. The production of oil, gas and coal is to be affected by climate.

White and Hertz -Picciotto (1985), Haile (1988), Kalkstein (1988), Smith and Tirjak (1988) and Wiseman and Longstreth (1988) observed that the potential effects of climate change on human health have been inferred from correlation of health conditions with weather variable or seasonality. The impact of climate change on human health would increase value and reduce opportunities by interfering with education and the ability to work. Prolonged intense heat waves coupled with humidity may increase mortality and morbidity rates. World Bank 2001 concluded that increased death rate such as flooding, landslides and storms over 96% of disaster-related death in recent year taken place.

Another serious impact of climate change warming on human health is the spread and resurgence of certain infectious disease change in temperature and rainfall may change the geographic range of vector-borne diseases such as malaria and dengue fever. The continuous warming of the Earth's climate has created favorable conditions for parasitism, reproduction and propagation of pathogens, expanding extent and scope of prevalent and thereby aggravating the harm to the population.

Conclusion:-

The climate change will have many impact on natural ecosystem water temperature, energy and human health. In face of the global warming issue we should speed up the public exchange platform for building global climate change and health risk as well as step up public preventive awareness for the sake of protecting human health. To save water affecting from pollution due to climate change, we should constrict new dams and development of conventional sources of water. eg. desalinization, recycling of industrial, municipal and agricultural waste water and weather modification. Because the influence of climate change is very broad, we should gradually expand the scope of research in future studies and establish partnership among countries. Apart from the above effects, government agencies, intergovernmental and non-governmental agencies should give play to their respective expertise trying their bests to carry out joint research.

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